

An in-vitro study to evaluate the accuracy of master casts obtained from different transfer impression techniques for a multi-unit implant restoration using two different impression materials evaluated by a 3-D optical scanner.

Perna Kaushik¹, Manesh Lahori², Shikha Shahi³, Siddharth Sisodiya⁴, Abhinav Agarwal⁴, Neha Srivastava¹.

¹Reader, Department of Prosthodontics, K. D. Dental College and Hospital, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India.

²Dean and Head, Department of Prosthodontics, K. D. Dental College and Hospital, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India.

³Post graduate student, Department of Prosthodontics, K. D. Dental College and Hospital, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India.

⁴Professor, Department of Prosthodontics, K. D. Dental College and Hospital, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Abstract

Background: The precise transfer of implant positions from the oral cavity to the working cast is critical for the passive fit of implant-supported prostheses. This study aimed to evaluate and compare the accuracy of master casts obtained through various impression techniques using two elastomeric materials—Polyvinyl Siloxane (PVS) and Polyether (PE)—assessed using a 3D optical scanning system (DWOS).

Materials and Methods: An edentulous maxillary reference model with four internal connection implants was used. Forty impressions were made using custom trays and categorized into eight groups (n=5 each) based on impression technique (closed/open tray), coping modification (non-modified, sandblasted, or splinted), and impression material (PVS or PE). Master casts were fabricated from each impression, and positional accuracy of implant analogues was evaluated using a DWOS 3D scanner by measuring horizontal distances between implants 2–3 and 1–4. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA.

Results: The mean reference distances between implants 2–3 and 1–4 were 1.308" and 2.748", respectively. Although variations were observed across different groups, the differences in accuracy were not statistically significant. Splinted copings exhibited the highest accuracy, followed by sandblasted and non-modified copings. Polyether impressions showed slightly better agreement with the reference model, but the difference was not statistically significant.

Conclusion: Within the limitations of this in vitro study, both PVS and PE impression materials yielded clinically acceptable accuracy in transferring implant positions. Non-splinted, non-modified impression copings provided comparable results, offering a simpler and more time-efficient approach. Further clinical studies are necessary to validate these findings under intraoral conditions.

Keywords: 3D Optical Scanning, Dental Implants, Impression Techniques, Impression Materials, Prosthetic Fit.

Address of correspondence: Perna Kaushik, Reader, Dept. Of Prosthodontics, K.D. Dental College & Hospital.

Email address: - perna912.kaushik@gmail.com **Phone no:** 9582456034. **DOI:** 10.5281/zenodo.15557573

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Introduction

Achieving success in oral rehabilitation necessitates the precise registration of anatomical structures that support prostheses. Therefore, it is imperative to accurately capture the three-dimensional orientation of dental implants, as this step lays the foundation for fabricating a well-fitting prosthesis.^[1]

Natural teeth possess the ability to move within the periodontal ligament by approximately 100 µm, which provides a buffer against minor misfits in fixed restorations. In contrast, osseointegrated implants, due to the rigidity of their bone integration, permit only minimal movement—around 10 µm. Consequently, any misfit in implant-supported prostheses may generate

internal stresses, adversely affecting the surrounding bone and soft tissues.^[1-3] Various impression techniques have been proposed to fabricate definitive casts that promote passive fit of implant-supported restorations. This pursuit for optimal accuracy has led to the adoption of different materials and transfer methods.^[4] The present study aims to compare the accuracy of master casts derived using PVS and Polyether impression materials, each evaluated using a 3D optical scanning system (DWOS), for multi-unit implant restorations.

Aim

To evaluate and compare the accuracy of master casts obtained through different impression transfer techniques using Polyvinyl Siloxane and Polyether impression materials, assessed using the DWOS 3D optical scanner.

Materials and methods

Reference Model Fabrication

A maxillary edentulous model was created using acrylic resin (DPI, India). Four internal connection implants (3.75 × 11 mm, ADIN Dental Implant Systems Ltd., Israel) were embedded and numbered 1 to 4 (left to right). For consistent tray placement, three indexing notches (two anterior, one posterior) were incorporated (Figure 1).

Custom Tray Fabrication

A type III stone primary cast (Figure 2) was produced from the reference model. Two layers of baseplate wax were placed over implant sites to standardize impression material thickness (Figure 3). An irreversible hydrocolloid impression was used to fabricate a secondary cast. Over this, a 2 mm thick thermoplastic sheet was adapted (Figure 4), and a two-part mold was formed using putty

silicone and the thermoplastic sheet inside a dental flask (Figure 5). The trays were fabricated using autopolymerizing resin and perforated to facilitate excess material escape (Figure 6). For open tray impressions, modifications were made to accommodate square impression copings (Figure 7 and 8).

Impression Procedure

Trays were coated with manufacturer-recommended tray adhesive and allowed to dry for 15 minutes. Copings were torqued to 10 N-cm using a calibrated wrench. A total of 40 impressions were made: 20 with PVS (Affinis, Coltene Whaledent, Monophase) and 20 with Polyether (3M ESPE, Monophase), using a one-step technique. After full seating of trays on indexing marks, impressions were allowed to polymerize for 12 minutes. For closed tray techniques, copings remained embedded within the impression. For open tray techniques, screws were loosened and copings were retained in the impression.

Study Groups

The impressions were categorized into 8 groups (n=5 per group):

Group 1: Non-modified closed tray copings + PVS

Group 2: Non-modified closed tray copings + Polyether

Group 3: Sandblasted closed tray copings + PVS

Group 4: Sandblasted closed tray copings + Polyether

Group 5: Non-modified open tray copings + PVS

Group 6: Non-modified open tray copings + Polyether

Group 7: Splinted copings + PVS

Group 8: Splinted copings + Polyether

Splinting Technique

Transfer copings were joined using four loops of dental floss (Figure 9) and splinted with autopolymerizing resin (Pattern Resin) (Figure 10). After polymerization, the splint was segmented into four parts with 0.2 mm gaps (Figure 11), then repositioned on the reference model and re-splinted (Figure 12).

Master Cast Fabrication

Implant analogues were attached to the impression copings, and casts were poured using type IV dental stone (Elite Rock, Zhermack) after 24 hours. Casts were demolded after 2 hours and stored for a minimum of 24 hours prior to scanning. All procedures were conducted by a single operator. Positional accuracy of implant analogues was assessed using DWOS 3D scanner.

Results

The mean reference inner distance (implants 2–3) was 1.308" (± 0.016), and the outer distance (implants 1–4) was 2.748" (± 0.013). Measurements from all groups were compared against these values. A one-way ANOVA was used to assess statistical differences between the eight groups. The 3D scanner facilitated precise measurement of positional deviation in implant analogues across all casts.

Discussion

Dentistry dates back to around 3000 BC, with Egypt recognized as an early medical hub.^[5] The first dental prosthesis appeared circa 2500 BC, and functional dentures were crafted by 700 BC. In medieval times, dentures were rare, often hand-carved and tied with silk, requiring removal before eating.^[6] Over time,

advancements in materials improved denture function, aesthetics, and comfort. The introduction of Branemark's implant-supported prostheses in 1982 significantly expanded treatment options for edentulous patients. A meta-analysis reported a 94.5% survival rate for single-tooth implants after five years.^[7]

The present study aimed to assess the accuracy of implant impressions using various combinations of impression techniques, coping modifications, and elastomeric materials. Eight groups were created using both direct (open tray) and indirect (closed tray) methods, with square impression copings that were either unmodified, sandblasted, or splinted. Two impression materials—PolyVinyl Siloxane (PVS) and PolyEther (PE)—were used in a monophasic, one-step technique with custom trays to ensure uniform material thickness and minimize distortion.^[8]

Results demonstrated that the type of impression material, coping modification, or splinting did not significantly influence the accuracy of implant position transfer. Both PVS and PE showed acceptable dimensional stability, with PVS offering easier handling and removal, especially in cases with nonparallel implants. While splinting copings is often advocated to reduce movement during impression making, it proved time-consuming and did not provide a clear advantage in accuracy. Sandblasting the copings also showed no substantial improvement over unmodified copings.

The study concludes that non-splinted, non-modified square impression copings used with either PVS or PE can produce clinically acceptable results, making them a practical and efficient option, particularly for immediate loading situations where ease and speed are critical. However, exact reproduction of implant positions remains challenging, highlighting the need for

continued advancements in materials and techniques.

Conclusion

Within the confines of this in vitro study, the following conclusions were derived:

Among the tested methods, splinted impression copings demonstrated the highest accuracy, followed by sandblasted and non-modified copings.

Although Polyether impressions yielded measurements closer to the reference model, the differences among the groups were not statistically significant. The selection of impression techniques may be guided by the specific clinical scenario and the clinician's judgment. Further clinical research is recommended to substantiate the findings of this study.

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TABLES**Table I horizontal distance between implant no. 2-3**

GROUP	N	MEAN	S.D.	t-value	p-value
CONTROL		1.308	0.016		
CLOSE TRAY NON-MODIFIED POLYVINYL SILOXANE	5	1.412	0.142	10.00	<0.05
CLOSE TRAY NON-MODIFIED POLY ETHER	5	1.336	0.025	1.240	>0.005
CLOSE TRAY MODIFIED POLY VINYL SILOXANE	5	1.399	0.143	0.143	>0.005
CLOSE TRAY MODIFIED POLY ETHER	5	1.347	0.015	3.162	<0.005
OPEN TRAY NON-MODIFIED POLY VINYL SILOXANE	5	1.347	0.021	3.162	<0.005
OPEN TRAY NON-MODIFIED POLY ETHER	5	1.326	0.014	2.00	<0.005
OPEN TRAY MODIFIED POLY VINYL SILOXANE	5	1.317	0.044	0.500	>0.005
OPEN TRAY MODIFIED POLY ETHER	5	1.3122	0.06	2.372	<0.005

Table II horizontal distance between implant no. 1-4

GROUP	N	MEAN	S.D.	t-value	p-value
CONTROL		2.748	0.013		
CLOSE TRAY NON-MODIFIED POLYVINYL SILOXANE	5	2.980	0.259	16.263	<0.005
CLOSE TRAY NON-MODIFIED POLY ETHER	5	2.815	0.044	3.254	<0.005
CLOSE TRAY MODIFIED POLY VINYL SILOXANE	5	2.972	0.259	1.891	>0.005
CLOSE TRAY MODIFIED POLY ETHER	5	2.810	0.050	2.631	<0.005
OPEN TRAY NON-MODIFIED POLY VINYL SILOXANE	5	2.827	0.031	5.657	<0.005
OPEN TRAY NON-MODIFIED POLY ETHER	5	2.813	0.035	3.254	<0.005
OPEN TRAY MODIFIED POLY VINYL SILOXANE	5	2.709	0.056	2.206	<0.005
OPEN TRAY MODIFIED POLY ETHER	5	2.709	0.038	3.536	<0.005

Graph 1 – Comparison between close tray and open tray impressions made from different techniques and impression materials for implant no. 2-3

Graph 2 – Comparison between close tray and open tray impressions made from different techniques and impression materials for implant no. 1-4.

FIGURES

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

